

TWO SPECIAL GRAPHS FOR δ -B-OPEN SETS

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ABSTRACT

We introduce the concepts δ -b-closed graphs and contra δ -b-closed graphs for δ b-open sets and obtain some properties of them.

Keywords: δ b-open sets, δ -b-closed graphs, contra δ -b-closed graphs, contra δ -b-continuous functions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Some various of sets is important in topological spaces as they are studied desely. Several topologists introduced and studied types generalizations properties and conditions containing them in topological spaces. In this paper, we introduce two special graphs related to δ b-open sets and investigate some properties of them.

In this study, spaces (Y, ξ) and (Z, ω) (briefly, Y and Z) always state topological spaces without any separation axiom. If $S \subseteq Y$, closure and interior of S in X are indicated by $Cl(S)$ and $Int(S)$ respectively. Since the concept of regular open sets is important several in branches of mathematics, recall it. A subset S is called be regular open if $S = Int(Cl(S))$. Similarly, a subset S is called be regular closed[11] if $(Y - S)$ is a regular open. In other words, a subset S is regular closed[11] iff $S = Cl(Int(S))$. The δ -interior of a subset S of Y is the union of all regular op. sets of Y contained S and it is indicated by $\delta - Int(S)$. S is called δ -open[12] iff $S = \delta - Int(S)$. In other words, S is called δ -open iff for each $y \in S$, there exists a regular open set R so that $y \in R \subseteq S$. Besides, δ -open sets in Y forms a topology ξ_δ so that $\xi_\delta \subseteq \xi$ and the regular open sets of Y form a base for ξ_δ . The δ - closure of a subset S of Y is the intersection of all regular closed sets of Y containing S and it is indicated by $\delta - Cl(S)$. S is called δ -closed[12] iff $S = \delta - Cl(S)$.

As a sequel, we need the next definitions and knowledges.

Definition 1.1. A subset S of a space (Y, ξ) is called

- (1) z -open[4] (or δ b-open[3]) if $S \subseteq Cl(\delta - Int(S)) \cup Int(Cl(S))$,
- (2) δ -semi-open[9] if $S \subseteq Cl(\delta - Int(S))$,
- (3) preopen[6] if $S \subseteq Int(Cl(S))$,
- (4) α -open[7] if $S \subseteq Int(Cl(Int(S)))$.

Remark 1.2. The next diagram holds for a subset S of a space Y . Each one of the converses of these implications isn't true in general. One can find the in related papers.

The δ -interior of a subset S of Y is the union of all δ b-open sets of Y contained S and it is indicated by δ -b- $Int(S)$. The complement of a δ b-open set is called δ b-closed. The δ -b-closure of a subset S of Y is the intersection of all δ b-closed sets of Y containing S and it is

indicated by δ b- $Cl(S)$ [5]. The family of all δ b-open subsets containing a point $y \in Y$ is denoted by $\delta BO(Y, y)$. The arbitrary union of any family of δ b-open sets in Y is a δ b-open set.[14]

Definition 1.3. A space (Y, ξ) is called

- (1) Urysohn[10] if for each $y_1, y_2 \in Y$ with $y_1 \neq y_2$, there exist open sets U and V so that $y_1 \in U, y_2 \in V$ and $Cl(U) \cap Cl(V) = \emptyset$.
- (2) δ -b- T_1 [5] if for each $y_1, y_2 \in Y$ with $y_1 \neq y_2$, there exist δ b-open sets U and V so that $y_1 \in U, y_2 \in V, y_1 \notin V, y_2 \notin U$.
- (3) δ -b- T_2 [5] if for each $y_1, y_2 \in Y$ with $y_1 \neq y_2$, there exist δ b-open sets U and V so that $y_1 \in U, y_2 \in V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$.

Definition 1.4. A mapping $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is called

- (1) δ b-continuous[4] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is δ b-open in Y for every open sets V of Z .
- (2) δ b-open[5] if $f(U)$ is δ b-open in Z for every open sets U of Y .

2. CHARACTERIZATIONS δ -B-CLOSED AND CONTRA δ -B-CLOSED GRAPHS

Firstly, it is well known that the subset $\{(y, f(y)) \mid y \in Y\} \subseteq Y \times Z$ for a mapping $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is called the graph of f and is denoted via G_f .

Definition 2.1. The graph G_f of a mapping $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is said to be

- (1) δ -b-closed if for each $(y, z) \in [(Y \times Z) - G_f]$, there exist δ -b-op. set $A \subseteq Y$ and open set $B \subseteq Z$ such that $y \in A, z \in B$ and $(A \times B) \cap G_f = \emptyset$.
- (2) contra δ -b-closed if for each $(y, z) \in [(Y \times Z) - G_f]$, there exist δ -b-op. set $A \subseteq Y$ and closed set $B \subseteq Z$ such that $y \in A, z \in B$ and $(A \times B) \cap G_f = \emptyset$.

Proposition 2.2. Let $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ be a map. Then the graph G_f of f is δ -b-closed in $(Y \times Z)$ iff for each $(y, z) \in [(Y \times Z) - G_f]$ there exist $A \in \delta BO(Y, y)$ and $B \in \varphi (z \in B)$ such that $f(A) \cap B = \emptyset$.

Proof. We must prove that $f(A) \cap B = \emptyset$ iff $(A \times B) \cap G_f = \emptyset$. Assume that $(A \times B) \cap G_f \neq \emptyset$. Then there exist $(y, z) \in (Y \times Z)$ such that $(y, z) \in (A \times B), z \neq f(y)$ and $(y, z) \in G_f$. Therefore, one can obtain $f(y) \in f(A)$ from $y \in A$. In this state; since $f(y) \in f(A)$ and $z \in B, f(A) \cap B \neq \emptyset$.

Proposition 2.3. The graph G_f of a mapping $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is contra δ -b-closed in $(Y \times Z)$ iff for each $(y, z) \in [(Y \times Z) - G_f]$ there exist $A \in \delta BO(Y, y)$ and

$B \in \omega^i(z \in B)$ such that $f(A) \cap B = \emptyset$ (ω^i denotes the family all closed sets in (Z, ω)).

Proof. This proof is similar to that of Proposition 2.2.

Theorem 2.4. If $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is contra δ -b-continuous and (Z, ω) is Urysohn space, then G_f is contra δ -b-closed in $(Y \times Z)$.

Proof. Suppose that $(y, z) \in [(Y \times Z) - G_f]$. Then, according to definition of graph map, $z \neq f(y)$ and since (Z, ω) is Urysohn space, there exist open sets $F, G \subseteq Y$ such that $f(x) \in F$, $y \in G$ and $\text{Cl}(F) \cap \text{Cl}(G) = \emptyset$. Besides since f is contra δ -b-continuous, there exist $A \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y)$ where $f(A) \subseteq \text{Cl}(F)$. This implies that $f(A) \cap \text{Cl}(G) = \emptyset$. Then by using Proposition 2.3, G_f is contra δ -b-closed in $(Y \times Z)$.

Theorem 2.5. If $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is δ -b-continuous and (Z, ω) is T_1 -space, then G_f is contra δ -b-closed in $(Y \times Z)$.

Proof. Let $(y, z) \in [(Y \times Z) - G_f]$. Hence $z \neq f(y)$ and since (Z, ω) is T_1 -space, there exist $B \in \omega$ such that $f(y) \in B$ and $z \notin B$. Besides, since f is δ -b-continuous, of course there exist $A \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y)$ such that $f(A) \subseteq B$. Therefore, we have $f(A) \cap (Z - B) = \emptyset$ and $B \in \omega^i(z \in B)$. Finally, one obtains that G_f is contra δ -b-closed in $(Y \times Z)$ via Proposition 2.3.

Lemma 2.6. ([5]) Let (Y, ξ) be a topological space and A, B be two subsets of X . If $A \in \delta\text{BO}(Y)$ and $B \in \delta\text{BO}(Y)$, then $(A \cap B) \in \delta\text{BO}(Y)$.

Theorem 2.7. Let $f, g: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ be functions and (Z, ω) is Urysohn space. If f is contra δ -b-continuous and g is contra super continuous, then $A = \{y \in Y: f(y) = g(y)\}$ is δ -b-closed in Y .

Proof. Let $y \notin A$. It is obvious that $f(y) \neq g(y)$. Since (Z, ω) is Urysohn space, there exist open sets $U, V \subseteq Z$ such that $f(y) \in U$, $g(y) \in V$ and $\text{Cl}(U) \cap \text{Cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Also f is contra δ -b-continuous and g is contra super continuous then $f^{-1}(\text{Cl}(U))$ is a δ -b-open sets and $g^{-1}(\text{Cl}(V))$ is a δ -open in Y , respectively. Take $M = f^{-1}(\text{Cl}(U))$ and $N = g^{-1}(\text{Cl}(V))$, then M and N are subsets of Y containing y . Set $K = M \cap N$, then K is δ -b-open sets in Y according to Lemma 2.6. Therefore, we have $f(K) \cap g(K) = f(M \cap N) \cap g(M \cap N) \subseteq f(M)$. Consequently, we have $A \cap K = \emptyset$ and thus $y \notin \delta\text{b-cl}(A)$. Hence, $\delta\text{b-cl}(A) \subseteq A$. This shows that A is δ -b-closed in Y .

Theorem 2.8. Let $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is a surjective which has δ -b-closed graph function. Then, (Z, ω) is T_1 -space.

Proof. Assume that $z_1, z_2 \in Z$ when $z_1 \neq z_2$. Since f is a surjective function, there exists an $y_1 \in Y$ so that $f(y_1) = z_1$ and $f(y_1) \neq z_2$. Hence $(y_1, z_2) \notin G_f$ and so via Proposition 2.2, there exist $A_1 \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y_1)$ and $B_1 \in \omega(z_2 \in B_1)$ so that $f(A_1) \cap B_1 = \emptyset$. Then $z_1 \in f(A_1)$, but $z_1 \notin B_1$. In similar way, there exists a $y_2 \in X$ so that $f(y_2) = z_2$ and $f(y_2) \neq z_1$. Then, $(y_2, z_1) \notin G_f$ and using Proposition 2.2, there exist $A_2 \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y_2)$ and $B_2 \in \omega(z_1 \in B_2)$ so that $f(A_2) \cap B_2 = \emptyset$. Hence $z_2 \in f(A_2)$ but $z_2 \notin B_2$. Therefore, $B_1 \in \omega(z_2 \in B_1)$ and $B_2 \in \omega(z_1 \in B_2)$ but $z_1 \notin B_1$ and $z_2 \notin B_2$. This shows that (Z, ω) is T_1 -space.

Theorem 2.9. If $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is δ -b-open and surjective function and G_f is δ -b-closed graph, then (Z, ω) is δ -b- T_2 -space.

Proof. Let $z_1, z_2 \in Y$ when $z_1 \neq z_2$. Since f is a surjective function, there exists an $y_1 \in Y$ so that $f(y_1) = z_1$ and $f(y_1) \neq z_2$. Hence $(y_1, z_2) \notin G_f$ and then there exist $A \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y_1)$ and $B \in \omega(z_2 \in B)$ so that $f(A) \cap B = \emptyset$ by utilizing Proposition 3.2. Since f is δ -b-open function, $f(A)$ is δ -b-open set containing z_1 . According to Diagram, B is a δ -b-open set containing z_2 . Hence, (Z, ω) is δ -b- T_2 -space.

3. FUNDAMENTAL PROPERTIES OF STRONGLY CONTRA δ -b-CLOSED GRAPHS

In this part, we introduce another class of graphs, namely, strongly contra δ -b-closed graphs and investigate various properties concerning of such this class of generalized graphs.

Definition 3.1. ([2]) The graph G_f of a function $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ will be termed δ -b-strongly closed if for each $(y, z) \in [(Y \times Z) - G_f]$, there exist $A \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y)$ and $B \in \omega(z \in B)$ such that $(A \times \text{Cl}(B)) \cap G_f = \emptyset$.

Regarding the strongly contra δ -b-closed graph, we can the following lemma.

Lemma 3.2. The graph G_f of a function $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is strongly contra δ -b-closed in $Y \times Z$ if for each $(y, z) \in [(Y \times Z) - G_f]$, there exist $A \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y)$ and $B \subseteq Z$ is regular closed ($z \in B$) such that $f(A) \cap B = \emptyset$.

Definition 3.3. ([2]) A function $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ will be termed weakly δ -b-continuous if each $y \in Y$ and for each open set B of Z containing $f(y)$, there exist $A \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y)$ such that $f(A) \subseteq \text{Cl}(B)$.

Theorem 3.4. Let $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is weakly δ -b-continuous function and (Z, ω) is Urysohn space, then G_f is δ -b-strongly closed.

Proof. Let $(y, z) \in [(Y \times Z) - G_f]$. According to definition of G_f , $z \neq f(y)$. Since (Z, ω) is Urysohn, there exist open sets $U, V \subseteq Z$ such that $f(y) \in U$, $z \in V$ and $\text{Cl}(U) \cap \text{Cl}(V) = \emptyset$. Besides since f is weakly δ -b-continuous, there exists $A \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y)$ so that $f(A) \subseteq \text{Cl}(U)$ and $f(A) \cap \text{Cl}(V) = f(A) \cap \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(V)) = \emptyset$ is a regular closed set in Z . Consequently, using Lemma 3.2, obtained that G_f is δ -b-strongly closed.

Definition 3.5. ([8]) A function $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ will be termed almost δ -b-continuous if $f^{-1}(B)$ is δ -b-open set in Y for every regular open set B of Z .

Lemma 3.6. ([8]) A function $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is almost δ -b-continuous iff each $y \in Y$ and for each regular open set B of Z containing $f(y)$, there exist $A \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y)$ such that $f(A) \subseteq B$.

Theorem 3.7. If $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is almost δ -b-continuous and (Z, ω) is T_2 -space, then G_f is δ -b-strongly closed in $(Y \times Z)$.

Proof. Consider $(y, z) \in [(Y \times Z) - G_f]$. Thus $z \neq f(y)$. Since (Z, ω) is T_2 -space; there exist open sets $U, V \subseteq Z$ such that $f(y) \in U$, $z \in V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. This is equivalent to $\text{Cl}(U) \cap \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(V)) = \emptyset$. Besides, since f is almost δ -b-continuous and V is regular open, then there exists $W \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y)$ so that $f(W) \subseteq V \subseteq \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(V))$ via Lemma

3.6. This implies that $f(W) \cap \text{Cl}(U) = \emptyset$ and consequently by using Lemma 3.2, we obtain G_f is strongly contra δ -b-closed in $(Y \times Z)$.

To obtain next two theorems, now we give a definition which is related to δ -b-closed set and characterizations of this notion.

Definition 3.8. A function $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ will be termed contra δ -b-continuous if $f^{-1}(B)$ is δ -b-closed set in Y for every open set B of Z .

The next theorem can be obtained by using the same technique of the similar result involving δ b-continuity.

Theorem 3.9. For a function $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$, the following properties are equivalent:

- (1) f is contra δ -b-continuous;
- (2) For every closed subset C of Z , $f^{-1}(C)$ is δ -open set in Y ;
- (3) For each $y \in Y$ and each closed subset C of Z containing $f(y)$, there exists $B \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y)$ such that $f(B) \subseteq C$.

Theorem 3.10. If G_f is contra δ -b-continuous, then $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is contra δ -b-continuous.

Proof. Consider U is an open set of Z , then $Y \times U$ is an open set of $Y \times Z$. According to hypothesis G_f is contra δ -b-continuous, we have $f^{-1}(U) = g^{-1}(Y \times U)$ is δ -b-closed in Y . Therefore, f is contra δ -b-continuous.

Definition 3.11. ([1]) A function $f: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ is called contra-super-continuous if for each $y \in Y$ and each closed subset C of Z containing $f(y)$, there exists $B \in \delta\text{BO}(Y, y)$ such that $f(B) \subseteq C$.

Definition 3.12. A subset A of a space (Y, ξ) will be termed a δ -b-dense in Y if $\delta\text{b-c}(A) = Y$.

Theorem 3.13. Let $f, g: (Y, \xi) \rightarrow (Z, \omega)$ be any two functions, (Z, ω) be an Urysohn space and $B \subseteq Y$ be a δ -b-dense set. If f is contra δ -b-continuous and g is contra super continuous, $f=g$ on B , then $f=g$ on X .

Proof. Since f is contra δ -b-continuous, g is contra super continuous and (Z, ω) is Urysohn; we have $A = \{y \in Y : f(y) = g(y)\}$ is δ -b-closed in Y according to

Theorem 2.6. By hypothesis, $f=g$ on B , $B \subseteq A$. Besides, B is δ -b-dense set in (Y, ξ) we get $Y = \delta\text{b-Cl}(B) \subseteq \delta\text{b-Cl}(A) = A$. This shows that $f=g$ on Y .

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